

Deliverable 5.1 Evaluation Methodology and Plan V1.0

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Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
AHP	Analytical Hierarchic Process
API	Application Programming Interface
CCAM	Connective, Cooperative, Autonomous Mobility
CEA	Cost-Effectiveness Analysis
CMR	Customer-managed relationship
DTLF	Digital Transport and Logistics Forum
EC	European Commission
EIA	Experience & impact assessment
EMR	Evaluation Manager
ETA	Estimated Time Arrival
FOT	Field Operation Test
ITU	Intermodal transport unit
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PCS	Port Community System
PM	Particulate Matters
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant and Time-bunded
SQ	Study Question
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
TOS	Transport Operational System
UC	Use Case
WP	Work Package

Document history

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Executive Summary

This document provides a guide for assessing the impact of the proposed solutions in real-world logistics operations. It details the methodology, metrics, and evaluation framework used to balance the effectiveness, efficiency, and uptake of KEYSTONE's digital solution. It ensures that the project's goals are achieved while aligning with European digitalization and sustainability objectives. As such, it shall serve as a handbook for subsequent activities throughout the assessment phase.

The document begins with an introduction that covers the project overview, purpose, audience, and structure. It then explains the evaluation methodology, which is based on the V-scheme of the field operation test (FOT) analysis and adapted for KEYSTONE. This schema divides the evaluation process into three phases: preparation, execution, and evaluation. The first phase "preparation", defines the methodology objectives, the definition and role of the evaluation managers (physical persons responsible for coordinating and overseeing the process across the use cases' activities within KEYSTONE) and the specifications of the two use cases (Intermodal digital ecosystem and Road transport digital ecosystem), along with 16 key performance analysis (KPIs) and study questions for measuring the project's impacts; the second phase "execution" covers solution deployment and data collection; while the last phase "evaluation" focuses on the measures for KPIs, incorporating advanced assessment methods like the analytical hierarchic process (AHP) and the cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA).

Finally, the evaluation methodology proposes an implementation time-plan in coordination with the pilot sites, which outlines the timeline for data collection and evaluation.

The methodology described in the present document is delivered during M23 and it outlines the guidelines that should be followed in the subsequent evaluation phases of the two use cases, once the piloting phase (WP4) is completed. Particularly, it will be thoroughly applied for the future development of D5.2 Evaluation of the impacts of the solutions proposed, whose submission is foreseen on M31 (December 2025).

1. Introduction

This deliverable focuses on evaluating the impact of its proposed solutions within real-world logistics operations. It outlines the methodology, indicators, and assessment framework used to measure the effectiveness, efficiency, and adoption of KEYSTONE digital solutions. This document ensures that the project's objectives are met while aligning with European digitalization and sustainability goals and it must be taken as a guide for the following activities during the assessment period.

The evaluation framework presented here builds on best practices from previous European logistics initiatives and incorporates methodologies, which enable a comprehensive assessment of the technological, operational, and socio-economic dimensions of KEYSTONE solutions. This deliverable also defines the processes for data collection and management, ensuring accuracy, reliability, and relevance in assessing the project's outcomes.

Beyond technical evaluations, this document considers the broader impact of KEYSTONE, including its contribution to policy recommendations, stakeholder engagement, and the development of an interoperable digital logistics ecosystem. By systematically evaluating the project's implementation and results, the deliverable provides insights that will support future large-scale deployment and regulatory alignment at the European level.

1.1 KEYSTONE overview

KEYSTONE project is designed to accelerate the digital transformation of freight transport by introducing standardized, Plug & Play solutions that ensure seamless data exchange across logistics stakeholders.

The project tackles critical challenges related to data interoperability, regulatory compliance, and digital adoption by integrating an Application Programming Interface (API) standard and a web app. The main objectives of KEYSTONE are:

- to develop a seamless, intermodal, interoperable digital exchange of information between logistics stakeholders and enforcement authorities.
- to promote a collaborative and standardized approach among freight transport operators, terminals, and regulatory bodies.
- to reduce compliance logistics costs through automated and secure data-sharing mechanisms.
- to facilitate wide-scale adoption of digital logistics solutions across Europe, ensuring regulatory alignment and industry standardization.

The evaluation framework in KEYSTONE plays a crucial role in assessing the project's outcomes and validating its impact. The evaluation phase is structured to:

- measure the effectiveness of KEYSTONE's digital solutions in real-world logistics scenarios.
- assess the efficiency and reliability of the API Reference Model and Web App in facilitating data exchange and compliance verification.
- quantify the cost-effectiveness of the proposed solutions by comparing traditional logistics operations with KEYSTONE-enabled processes.
- identify and analyze the challenges and opportunities for full-scale implementation and regulatory integration.
- engage stakeholders and end-users to gather qualitative insights and ensure that the solutions meet industry needs.

By applying a structured evaluation approach of the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), stakeholder feedback, and comparative analyses, the project aims to provide actionable insights for policymakers,

logistics operators, and enforcement authorities. The findings will support the replication and scalability of KEYSTONE solutions across the European transport sector.

1.2 Purpose of this document

Deliverable 5.1 "Evaluation Methodology and Plan", as its name indicates, provides in general terms the methods and tools necessary for the evaluation of the project, this includes indicators, data management, and the basis of the reporting that will be worked on in the tasks and deliverables that follow task 5.1.

In the formation of this deliverable, the work carried out in almost 18 months of KEYSTONE is taken into consideration, including the study of the project bases, the architecture for the solution, and the development plans. In chronological terms, this deliverable is a pivot of the project, since at this point the understanding of the solution reaches a point of maturity necessary to be deployed in the pilots, so having a guide for the evaluation is fundamental.

1.3 Intended audience

The work presented in this deliverable aims to present the evaluation lines to all project partners, but it is emphasized that the partners of work packages 4 and 5 are the main audience. On the one hand, work package 4 is where the KEYSTONE solution will be implemented, so understanding what will be evaluated is essential for the layout of the use cases, since they must consider the data, and also its collection. This task will be supported by the evaluation managers on site, who will have direct contact and will be able to apply the methods described in this document for the collection of data and relevant information. On the other hand, the partners involved in the subsequent tasks of work package 5 need a guide for the evaluation of the tasks, which in many cases are directly related to the evaluation of the actions implemented in KEYSTONE.

In this context, deliverable 5.1 has been conceived under a cooperation scheme with the evaluation managers and partners involved in the entire assessment cycle of the project.

1.4 Structure of the document

The structure of the deliverable is developed following the V-scheme of the FOT (Field Operational Test), used in previous projects in the field of logistics such as AEOLIX or FENIX, and adapted to the requirements of KEYSTONE. For this reason, there is a chapter for each of the three phases conceived under the approach, that is, a preparation phase, execution phase, and evaluation phase. For each of them, some objectives must be defined. The fundamental phase that this deliverable focuses on is the initial one, where aspects such as methodology, indicators, and data collection methods are defined. Subsequently, the document defines the following stages so that work packages 4 and 5 can develop them effectively.

2. Evaluation methodology

2.1 Introduction to Evaluation Methodology

The overarching goal of KEYSTONE is to support the development of a sustainable, efficient, and safe transport system, allowing enforcement authorities to access data to check compliance with rules applied in the transport of goods and passengers.

The present document allows to assess whether the main KEYSTONE objectives were achieved, namely:

- Main objective 1: Contributing to safety standards,
- Main objective 2: Promoting collaboration among stakeholders,
- Main objective 3: Reducing compliance logistics costs,
- Main objective 4: Ensuring replication at the EU level,
- Main objective 5: Implementing API standardization.

More specifically, the evaluation framework is built to determine whether and to what extent the user needs and requirements have been addressed by the services offered by KEYSTONE. The model defines the evaluation requirements, the study questions, and the KPIs regarding both the pilots and the two user cases. Indeed, it was decided to develop a common evaluation Framework because it is extremely useful to clarify the content and methodologies of the evaluation sub-activities, enlightening their links to other actions within the project. Also, it can be used as a one-reference manual for all the pilot sites and their stakeholders, ensuring and facilitating the whole evaluation process.

As such, the related output will consequently guide the pilot by outlining the timeline and the requirements of the data collection on the one hand and support the Evaluation Manager (EM) with the assessment of the two use cases, on the other.

2.2 Common Evaluation Framework

The evaluation methodology has been developed following the V scheme of the FOT analysis, used in previous projects in the field of logistics such as AEOLIX (Renzi, et al., 2019) or FENIX (Renzi, Dell'Amico, & Di Gregorio, 2022), and here adapted to the requirements of KEYSTONE, as depicted below in Figure 1.

Figure 1 V scheme of the FOT (Field Operational Test) applied for KEYSTONE

KEYSTONE Common Evaluation Framework consists of three main phases.

- Preparation Phase: it includes several activities, preparatory for the next two. A detailed plan is developed, including the outlining of the project objectives, as well as the pilot sites and the definition of the two use cases (AS-IS). Furthermore, the hypotheses and expected impacts (TO-BE) are identified, the KPIs are defined, the Evaluator Managers (EM) are identified, and the data collection and management are structured.
- Execution Phase: the execution phase focuses on implementing solutions and initiating data processes. Deployment solutions are rolled out, ensuring systems are configured and operational while initial data loading and validation are enacted. Performance is monitored against KPIs by the EM to ensure the project stays on track. Real-time data and performance monitoring begin, to track

system functionality and identify any issues. Stakeholder engagement sessions are conducted to provide updates, gather feedback, and ensure alignment on progress and expectations.

- Evaluation Phase: it involves assessing project outcomes through detailed data analysis based on KPIs to measure success. Cost-Effectiveness Analysis (CEA) and Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) are utilized to evaluate alternatives and prioritize decisions. Insights from these analyses will subsequently guide the consolidation of recommendations, ensuring they are data-driven and actionable. This phase synthesizes findings to determine the project's impact and areas for improvement. Final recommendations are documented for stakeholders to inform future strategies.

3. Preparation phase

3.1 Definition of objectives

The preparation phase of the KEYSTONE evaluation framework aligns the intersection between the general objectives of the KEYSTONE project and the specific objectives of the pilot sites. KEYSTONE aims to enhance digitalization in logistics through standardized API solutions and a web app, fostering interoperability, reducing compliance costs, and improving enforcement efficiency. Meanwhile, the pilot sites serve as real-world testing environments where these innovations are implemented and assessed under distinct logistics scenarios.

The monomodal case, focuses on improving efficiency in road-based logistics, particularly in streamlining data exchange between logistics operators and enforcement authorities, while the intermodal case extends these objectives by testing the interoperability of digital solutions across multiple transport modes, including rail and road.

Through this intersection of objectives, the evaluation phase will focus on assessing:

- the extent to which the KEYSTONE API and web app improve data exchange and enforcement processes.
- the efficiency gains achieved in compliance procedures, measured through time saved in document verification and enforcement operations.
- the reduction in operational costs and environmental impact, aligned with KEYSTONE's sustainability goals.
- the scalability and replicability of the solutions, ensuring they can be widely adopted across different logistics contexts in the EU.

This structured approach ensures that the evaluation remains cohesive and targeted, linking the high-level vision of KEYSTONE with tangible improvements at the pilot site level. The subsequent chapters will outline the methodologies and KPIs used to measure these impacts effectively.

3.2 Evaluation Manager

The EMs are the physical persons responsible for coordinating and overseeing the process across the use cases' activities within KEYSTONE. The EMs are key figures responsible for ensuring the application and consistency of the evaluation framework, acting as the primary point of contact between the technical team and the UC, and aligning activities with the overall project objectives.

The primary responsibilities of the EM include:

- coordination of evaluation activities: ensuring that the UC follows the evaluation methodology and framework, facilitating collaboration between technical and operational partners for consistent data collection and reporting
- monitor and track of Indicators: overseeing the identification, measurement, and tracking of indicators to assess the performance and impacts of the solutions proposed in the respective UC.
- report and feedback: providing regular updates to the evaluation task leaders, including feedback on the evaluation progress, discrepancies, and recommendations for improving the evaluation process
- ensuring compliance: ensuring that the activities running under the UC are complied with the agreed-upon methodologies and align with KEYSTONE's goals, including ethical, legal, and data management guidelines, described in the previous chapter 2.5

KEYSTONE has defined four EMs, two per UC, either the role is not an official position among the consortium, or it is expected to collaborate with the partners of the evaluation process. The EMs per UC are listed in Table 1.

Table 1 Evaluation Managers per UC

Use Case	EM	Partner	Brief Biography
UC1	Valentina Scandura	Gruber Logistics	Division Manager FTL Road Intermodal at Gruber Logistics, 11 years of operational experience in logistics and transport.
	Fabrizio Bergogna	Gruber Logistics	Fabrizio Bergogna specializes in market analysis, strategy consultancy, estimates of territorial needs and in research and data processing, in particular on socio-economic indicators and trade flows and traffic. With an in-depth knowledge of inland transport and maritime-port realities and their dynamics, he has contacts with both public and private terminal managers, transport companies, and research institutions. He also deals with teaching and training in the logistics and transport sector.
UC2	Laura Pappalardo	CIM	Laura Pappalardo is a licensed surveyor with 19 years of experience in technical drawing and project management, specializing in AutoCAD for residential and industrial lighting. She has led energy efficiency projects with companies like Electrolux and Geodis. Currently, she works at CIM on lighting redevelopment and maintenance in the interport sector, expanding her expertise in international projects.
	Massimo Arnesse	CIM	Massimo Arnese is an accountant with different specialisations in computer science and the structure of digital networks. His professional career began 24 years ago, when he joined a group specialising in international shipping. For 8 years, Massimo Arnese has been able to develop an important experience in transporting and storing goods. Combining a passion for digital and logistics, Masimo Arnese has proposed and implemented a series of projects for the digitalisation of transport procedures, in particular towards Austria and the countries of East Europe.

3.3 Use Case Definition

In the following subchapters, both use cases are defined, in order to have a big picture of the initial state, aiming for an appropriate definition of the indicators to assess the expected impact of the KEYSTONE’s solution. These definitions are based on the deliverable 4.2 of the KEYSTONE (Metta, Re Calegari, Agrawal , & Comerio, 2025) .

3.3.1 Use Case 1: Intermodal digital ecosystem

The first use case is the intermodal transport, which includes rail and road modes, this scenario involves goods departing from Rotterdam intermodal hub and traveling by train to CIM Novara terminal and then being loaded onto a truck for their final destination. During the road journey, the road police enforcer stops it to ensure compliance with regulations and the safety of the transport.

Table 2 breaks down the use case by applying a customer journey mapping tool.

Table 2 UC1: Customer Journey Mapping – Part 1

Element	Phase 1: Train planning and departure	Phase 2: Truck planning and departure	Phase 3: Train and Truck arrival	Phase 4: Truck Departure	Phase 5: In transit to final destination

			at Freight Terminal		
Transport mode	Train	Truck	Train and Truck	Truck	Truck
Main Actors	Departure Terminal Operator	Gruber Logistics Office	CIM terminal operator	Truck Driver	Road police enforcer
Key Actions	ITU (Intermodal transport unit) is prepared to be loaded in the train. ITU is loaded on the train. The train departs to reach CIM.	Gruber Logistics Office arrange the trucks and books the trips for ITU pickup to CIM freight terminal. The truck departs to CIM.	Train arrival. ITU is unloaded from the train. Check in truck and driver. ITU is loaded on truck.	Truck checks out	Control check by road police enforcer.
Description of actions	The Departure Terminal Operator prepares the train list and CMR related to the ITU, it carries out all checks and load ITU on the train. It also informs CIM about the departure time and ETA via an integrated platform (EDIGES).	Gruber Logistics office books the trip for ITU pickup and send authorised driver for the ITU pickup to CIM freight terminal.	When ITU arrives, CIM sends an update confirming the successful ITU unloading. At the same time, Gruber Logistics truck arrives to the terminal. And an automatic verification of driver's data starts (license plate, vehicle integrity, etc) through an OCR portal. Also, a manual verification of driver data is done using excel files and/or email. Lastly, the ITU is loaded on the truck.	Truck prepares for departure. Driver calls to Gruber Logistics Office to update about successful loading of goods and the departure of the truck from CIM freight terminal	Road police enforcer stops the truck for control and the driver shares the document (license, truck registration, goods documentation, etc), the Road police enforcer conducts the checks and truck inspection. If additional information is needed the driver calls to the company for verification
Touchpoints	TOS (WOLF/EDIGES), GPS (Carriages)	TOS (WOLF/EDIGES)	TOS (WOLF/EDIGES), Excel, Email	TOS (WOLF/EDIGES), Phone calls, paper documents	Enforcement Authorities System, Paper Documents
Data Involved	Train list (scheduled trains with goods) Train CMR (only for CIM) Train composition ITU list ADR Train closing and departure time Train ETA + Real Time ETA and	Driver data (name, last name) Trucks data (Authorised by X company, license plate).	Train actual arrival Truck actual arrival ITU unloading and loading status MAD/ETP (Estimate Time for Pickup) ITU Pickup.	ITU pickup exit date/time ITU Gate-out interchange (physical document for the driver).	Truck's data Driver data ITU data.

	update ETA (via EDGES).				
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In each phase, there are pain points and opportunities to solve the problem through the KEYSTONE’s solution, as Table 3 shows.

Table 3 UC1: Customer Journey Mapping – Part 2

Element	Phase 1: Train planning and departure	Phase 2: Truck planning and departure	Phase 3: Train and Truck arrival at Freight Terminal	Phase 4: Truck Departure	Phase 5: In transit to final destination
Pain Points	ETA from Train cannot be shared with third parties, only with CIM due to limitation of EDIGES system.	Train ETA is not used by Gruber Driver in case of delay or disruption. There is not a repository of the authorised drivers.	TOS is integrated with few customer’s systems as not all customers have digital documents to provide. Also, there are no real time update for loading and unloading operations.	There is no real time information about when the truck leaves the freight terminal, either for Road police enforcer as for Logistic Company.	Paper documents consume a lot of time for the check, beside they need to connect to different system to check, and there is no possibility to checking truck without stopping it as there is no data available about flow of truck on road to setup the check points. Many sources of information and many documents.
Opportunities	Sharing of real-time forecast data regarding to train’s journey to truck companies can enhance a better planning for picking up. A unique platform with possibilities to share API to all customers for a better planning for the ITU pickup.	As it was mentioned before, the ETA for drivers will improve planning. Also, a digital repository would aim for a fast verification at CIM freight terminal	Improvement of information exchange between actors, for loading/unloading and picking up status.	Automatization of the process of capturing information/data about the truck and goods by tracking real time location of trucks.	It is needed a solution for remotely control with a unique entry point to different systems and digital repository of all required paper documents available in unique system. Information is digitalized in a unique digital ecosystem.

3.3.2 Use Case 2: Road transport digital ecosystem

This second scenario focuses on the road transportation of a container from northern Italy to the Port of La Spezia, with the goal of establishing a data exchange with the port authority. KEYSTONE aims to focus on integrating the platforms used by Gruber Logistics and the Port of La Spezia to facilitate and optimize logistics operations, as well as enhance regulatory oversight.

Table 4 breaks down the use case by applying a customer journey mapping tool.

Table 4 UC2: Customer Journey Mapping – Part 1

Element	Truck departure before	Truck Departure	Truck in transit	Truck arrival at the port
Transport mode	Truck	Truck	Truck	Truck
Main Actors	Gruber Logistics Office	Gruber Logistics Driver	Gruber Logistics Driver	Port La Spezia authority
Key Actions	The shipping of a ITU is planned and the related documentation is prepared.	The ITU is loaded on the truck, which starts the trip toward the Port of La Spezia.	The ITU is carried to the Terminal by the truck.	The truck arrives at the Port gate. Checks and controls are carried out for managing safety and traffic issues.
Description of actions	As road transport operator (and not necessarily as freight forwarder), Gruber Logistics prepares the documents related to the container according to the CMR. They also send the driver to the customer.	Truck arrives at the customer. Gruber Logistics driver updates the Gruber Logistics office about the (i) successful loading of the container on the truck, and (ii) the time of departure of the truck.	Gruber Logistics driver is carrying the container to be unloaded.	Port checks the validity of the badge of Gruber Logistics Driver and ITU ID. Port authorises Gruber Logistics driver and the container to access the Port area and to arrive to the Terminal.
Touchpoints	TMS; Excel or other tools	TMS; Call.	Email; Call.	PCS; Call
Data Involved	CMR (sender, receiver, itinerary, carrier, place of taking over, place of destination, and description of goods, ITU ID)	ETA data is a static data generated by the TMS and according to the departure time. ETA is not updated nor shared dynamically ITU ID It is included in the CMR document. ETA is linked with the ITU ID and they are saved in the TM	ETA (eventually updated) In case of delay, Gruber Logistics office informs the Terminal about the updated ETA via email. The Gruber Logistics office is notified by the truck driver by call.	Check-in status The check-in data is generated by the Port.

In each phase, there are pain points and opportunities to solve the problem through the KEYSTONE’s solution, as Table 5 shows.

Table 5 UC2: Customer Journey Mapping – Part 2

Element	Phase 1: Truck before departure	Phase 2: Truck Departure	Phase 3: Truck in transit	Phase 4: Truck arrival at the port
Pain Points	Currently CMR is a paper document that is shared manually by the driver once the truck has arrived at its	Gruber Logistics does not send ETA of the container to the Port	ETA is created and sent manually. ETA data is not automatically generated.	Gruber Logistics is not automatically notified about the completed check-in. Gruber Logistics does not send

	destination (Port and/or Terminal)		Updated data might be not received or received with delay	information about the driver. The Port cannot ensure authorisation for the driver in advance. At the same time, the GL driver might be stopped at the Port gate because he does not have permissions to get in.
Opportunities	Digitizing the CMR document (e-CMR) for enabling the exchange of goods information between different stakeholders and using existing platforms		Provision of updated date to the Port. System of alerts available to the port authority to inform trucks about possible queues at the gate.	Advanced notice management platform to help port authority optimise the truck flow. Availability of driver's data to Port in advance.

3.4 Expected Impacts

KEYSTONE aims to address critical inefficiencies in multimodal transport by integrating digital solutions that enhance interoperability, regulatory compliance, and operational efficiency. The TO-BE scenario represents the envisioned future state of logistics operations following the implementation of the KEYSTONE solutions, providing a benchmark against which the project's impact can be measured.

The development of the scenario is based on several aspects, each aligned with the project's objectives such as improving data interoperability, reduction in compliance cost through digitalization, increasing efficiency in freight inspection and control procedures reduction of environmental impact through optimized operations, and increasing the adoption of digital solutions by stakeholders.

The expected impact of the developed scenario extends across multiple dimensions, including economic, operational, and environmental benefits, serving as the foundation for assessing KEYSTONE's overall impact, ensuring that the project's digital solutions drive measurable improvements in multimodal logistics operations.

3.5 KPIs and Study Questions

3.5.1 Definition of the initial set of KPIs and Study Questions

The identification of KPIs and study questions (SQs) for the assessment of KEYSTONE followed a structured and collaborative approach involving project partners and key stakeholders. This process was designed to ensure that the selected KPIs would effectively measure the project's objectives and impacts across multiple dimensions, including operational performance, environmental and social impact, and stakeholder engagement.

The development of the KPI framework was embedded in a common effort among the consortium members and relevant stakeholders, ensuring diverse perspectives and needs were integrated. The approach comprised:

- analysis of previous European projects related to the logistic environment, initiatives like FENIX, AEOLIX, and FEDERATED provided a foundational understanding of best practices, common challenges, and successful methodologies.

- analysis of similar solutions and their impact, especially related to API and web app, which were studied in terms of their expected functionalities and anticipated impacts, allowed to identify technical and operational performance and the metrics to measure them, while considering their ability to identify gaps in interoperability and data sharing.
- analysis of market and sustainability trends, focusing on technological advancement and regulatory compliance, to ensure that the selected metrics would be aligned with ongoing and future demands, supporting the scalability and long-term relevance of the KEYSTONE solution.

These iterative procurements led to the establishment of an initial set of KPIs and SQs that reflected the diverse impact areas of the project, incorporating operational and scenario-based performance, environmental and social impact, and stakeholder engagement. It is important to mention that each KPI was analysed using the SMART (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Relevant, and Time-bounded) approach, which helped to get more detailed information and foresee any issue ahead of time.

By collecting expertise, analysing past initiatives, and aligning with market and policy trends, the project has ensured a definition of 39 KPIs and 30 study questions providing a robust basis for evaluating its outcomes and identifying areas for further improvement. The preliminary list of KPIs and SQs are listed in Table 6.

Table 6 Study Questions and KPIs

Study question	KPI title	KPI description
How many stakeholders are actively contributing data on environmental emissions in the KEYSTONE project?	Number of actors providing data on environmental emissions	Measure the number of different stakeholders actively contributing data on environmental emissions.
What methodologies are currently being used for API standardization, and how can they inform the development of the API reference model in the context of KEYSTONE project?	Methodology Integration Effectiveness	Assess the effectiveness of integrating current methodologies for API standardization into the development of the API reference model.
	Ease of Services Mapping between End-Users	Measure the effectiveness of enabling end-users to map services without extensive programming and documentation, as per the KEYSTONE paradigm.
Which processes are outlined in the API reference model for retrieving information based on legislative requirements, and how are they applied to meet specific platform needs?	Compliance with Legislative Information Retrieval	Evaluate the degree to which the information retrieval processes outlined in the API reference model align with legislative requirements for accessing information from other platforms.
How are the new Business Models proposed by KEYSTONE defined, and what criteria are used to evaluate the effectiveness of the implemented Business Cases?	Effectiveness of Business Case Evaluation Criteria	Measure the effectiveness of the specific Business Cases implemented in the project.

How is the web app architecture designed to ensure both security and accessibility, and what considerations are made to maximize usability across different devices, including mobile, laptops, and tablets?	Security and Accessibility Measures	Measure the effectiveness of security and accessibility measures incorporated into the web app architecture.
	Universal Accessibility and Security	Evaluate the accessibility of the web app across various devices (mobile and desktop) and assess the security measures implemented to meet policing software standards.
To what extent is the web app accessible across devices, and how does it comply with policing software security standards?	End-Users Web App Usage	Evaluate the web app usage of end-users, including drivers, enforcement personnel, and logistics managers, and assess how well the web app caters to their specific needs.
How efficient is the data flow resulting from the implementation of API standards and the web app?	Data Flow Efficiency	Evaluation of efficiency in data flow resulting from the implementation of API standards and the web app through performance monitoring tools, data flow analysis, and periodic reviews.
What features and functionalities are included in the web app, and how well do they contribute to achieving KEYSTONE's overall goals?	Feature-rich Web App Development	Evaluate the richness of features and functionalities in the developed web app and assess how well they align with the goals of the KEYSTONE project.
How effectively is legal documentation managed within the web app, particularly in relation to vehicle and load compliance?	Efficient Legal Documentation Management	Measure the efficiency of the web app in managing legal documentation exchange within KEYSTONE API.
What validated safety and security mechanisms are in place within the KEYSTONE system, and how resilient are they across tested scenarios?	Validated Safety and Security System	Develop an innovative, efficient, consistent, and resilient system for validated safety and security in connected and automated mobility (CCAM) technologies and systems. Validate the system's robustness and resilience in two scenarios during the project.
How does the common evaluation plan ensure consistency and comparability between pilots and use cases, and how does it address scenario-specific evaluation needs?	Guiding Pilots with Evaluation Methodology	Measure the effectiveness of the evaluation methodology in guiding pilots, specifically in terms of outlining timelines and data collection requirements.

How is quality of life impacted by the implementation of KEYSTONE compared to the pre-project baseline?	Quality of Life Improvement	Improvement in the quality of life measured in terms of comparison between the pre-KEYSTONE and the post-KEYSTONE situation.
How much impact on the environment can be attributed to the implementation of KEYSTONE?	Energy savings (in kW)	Measure the amount of energy savings achieved in kilowatts (kW) before, during, and at the end of the KEYSTONE project.
	PM reduction	Monitor the reduction in particulate matter (PM) emissions before, during, and at the end of the KEYSTONE project.
	Fuel consumption	Track the reduction in fuel consumption before, during, and at the end of the KEYSTONE project.
How effective are the services and products enhanced through the KEYSTONE platform in meeting project objectives?	Quality of service indicator	Assess the efficiency of the services and products enhanced within KEYSTONE.
How do information management costs compare before and after the implementation of KEYSTONE?	Information management costs	Compare information management costs pre and post KEYSTONE implementation, aiming for a reduction in costs.
How many new business opportunities have been generated per pilot site through KEYSTONE implementation?	Number of business opportunities created	Number of business opportunities created - at least 3 per pilot site.
How does KEYSTONE contribute to increasing productivity in logistics and transport services across its pilot scenarios?	Logistics and Transport Services Productivity Increase	Achieve a minimum 15% increase in productivity for logistics and transport services compared to the estimated productivity.
How have working conditions improved for logistics personnel as a result of KEYSTONE implementation?	Working Conditions Improvement	Evaluate the improvement in working conditions based on the results of the CEA Conduct surveys and interviews among transport operators to gauge their appreciation and assess changes in productivity.
How many data sets are exchanged in real-time as a result of the KEYSTONE solution?	Number of data sets exchanged in real-time	Number of data sets exchanged in real-time - at least 5 per pilot.
What percentage of documents are exchanged digitally through the KEYSTONE web app compared to the total required?	% of Documents Exchanged Through Project web app	Measure the percentage of documents exchanged through the project web compared to all mandatory documents in each pilot.

How many use cases have been implemented under the "compliant by design" approach within the KEYSTONE project?	Number of Implemented "Compliant by Design" Use Cases	Assess the number of implemented "compliant by design" use cases within the project.
How much time has been saved in control procedures for transport operators through the use of the KEYSTONE web app?	Speeding up of control procedures thanks to the use of the web app	Evaluate the speeding up of control procedures transport operators through the use of the web app.
	Speeding up of data collection procedures of transport operators (average time for uploading data).	Evaluate the speeding up of data collection processes for transport operators through the use of the web app.
How do end-users perceive the new processes and tools introduced through the KEYSTONE platform?	Workers' appreciation of the new processes and tools	Evaluation of the KEYSTONE solutions by the end users.
How has productivity in data exchange improved?	Increased productivity in data exchange operations	Increase productivity in data exchange.
How many applications have been developed and tested during the pilot demonstrations of KEYSTONE?	Number of applications developed and tested in the use-case demonstrations;	Monitor the number of applications developed and tested in use-case demonstrations.
How many users have logged in and actively used the KEYSTONE platform since its launch?	Number of new logins	Monitor the number of new logs within the web app.
	Number of active users	Monitor the number of active users.
To what extent has KEYSTONE improved awareness among transport operators about general and local regulations and warnings?	Awareness of Transport Operators regarding Regulations and Warnings	Evaluate the awareness of transport operators regarding the full set of general and local regulations and warnings.
How many logistics procedures have been fully digitalized and automated as part of the value chain in KEYSTONE?	Number of automated procedures along the value chain	Quantify the number of procedures fully digitalized and automatically performed along the logistics value chain.
What specific gaps identified by the DTLF working group have been addressed in the KEYSTONE design process?	Integration of DTLF Findings	Evaluate how well the project integrates DTLF's main findings regarding Plug & Play needs of development into its design.
How effectively has the project fostered collaboration and	Seminars for Private Sector Engagement	Organize at least three seminars for the private sector, each lasting 60/90 minutes

community-building among private stakeholders, public entities, research institutions, and European networks, and what results have been achieved?		with at least three presenters, to facilitate engagement and collaboration.
	Building a Strong Public-Private Transport Community	Measure the strength and growth of the public-private transport community resulting from the project.
	Collaboration with Research Institutions	Establish collaboration with a minimum of 10 research institutions.
	KEYSTONE Community Creation	Create a KEYSTONE community including at least 20 European institutions active on the platform.

3.5.2 Review meeting’s feedback

During the online Review Meeting (M18) held on December 9th, 2024, the KEYSTONE Project Officer suggested reducing the number of KPIs from the 41 presented during the WP5 meeting (which included both the original KPIs defined during the proposal stage and those included in the grant agreement) to around 15 KPIs. This adjustment aims to focus exclusively on the project’s primary impacts, ensuring that the key results of KEYSTONE are measurable, shareable, and communicable.

As a result of this proposal, the next step was to schedule a meeting with the consortium, which took place on December 11th, 2024, to review relevant aspects and define the final list of KPIs. The final list of KPIs can now be found in the following subchapter “3.5.4 Key Performance Indicators”

3.5.3 Technical meetings with consortium and EMs

In the second week of December, a meeting was held with the consortium partners to streamline the list of indicators. This online meeting also served as an opportunity to present the evaluation framework.

During the session, all preliminary indicators were presented, analyzed, and discussed with both the individuals responsible for their measurement and the evaluation managers. Comments and feedback were gathered, leading to additional bilateral meetings and a physical meeting with the evaluation managers in Reggio Emilia. These discussions finalized the list of indicators, data collection and management methods, and the assessment approach.

3.5.4 Key Performance Indicators

The final list of indicators has been developed using the SMART, along with several meetings with each of the partners involved in the metric, which have been organized into three main groups:

- Operational Indicators
- Web app
- API

3.5.4.1 Operational Indicators

The selected indicators will be measured during the piloting phase, with their relevance rooted in their impact across multiple areas aligned with sustainable development goals. These include energy efficiency, fuel consumption, and emission reduction, among others. Additionally, the indicators address critical operational

aspects, such as improving data collection and processing, which are essential for enhancing market competitiveness.

The process of refining these indicators has involved direct engagement with the designated Evaluation Managers from the outset of the task. Their participation has followed a well-established participatory framework, encompassing monthly meetings as well as dedicated sessions. A key milestone in this process was the face-to-face workshop held on January 22, 2025, which provided a crucial platform for dialogue between the task leader and the evaluation managers. This workshop aimed to assign quantitative values to the KPIs, define hypotheses, and anticipate potential risks related to measurement.

Regarding the operations, the following KPIs are included in Table 7 :

Table 7 Operational KPIs – Time based

KPI ID and title	Description
KPI #1: Energy Saved	Reduction of 20% of the kW consumed yearly.
KPI #2: PM reduction	Reduction of 20% of total PM emissions per year.
KPI #3: Fuel consumption reduction	Reduction of 20% of fuel consumption per year.

These indicators are directly linked to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (UN General Assembly, 2015), specifically:

- SDG 7: Affordable and Clean Energy
- SDG 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities
- SDG 12: Responsible Consumption and Production
- SDG 13: Climate Action

For all the cases, the estimation of the time saved is an important aspect to consider for the estimation of the gap between baseline and implementation scenarios. The baselines will be calculated according to a yearly operation of the entire logistic process, from the truck arrival at the CIM freight terminal to the arrival at Port La Spezia, including both use cases in the process, and it will be based on the time saved on the different operations by using KEYSTONE solutions. All three metrics can be linked to the time by applying multiplication factors, for example, the estimated fuel saved can be translated in the following formula:

$$Fuel\ Savings\ (L) = Average\ Fuel\ Consumption\ \left(\frac{L}{hours}\right) \times Time\ Saved\ (hours)$$

In this case, the information needed is the average fuel consumption of the fleet, which may be estimated by assuming the average fuel consumption of heavy-duty vehicles, normally around 30 to 40 liters per hour, then the necessary information is also regarding the time of average working days/hours per year. For example, an average fuel consumption is 35 liters per hour and the time saved is 2 hours per day on a 250 working days yearly schema.

$$Fuel\ Savings\ (L) = 35\ \left(\frac{L}{hours}\right) \times 2\ \left(\frac{hours}{day}\right) \times 250\ \left(\frac{days}{year}\right)$$

$$Fuel\ Savings\ (L) = 70\ \left(\frac{L}{day}\right) \times 250\ \left(\frac{days}{year}\right)$$

$$\text{Fuel Savings (L)} = 17500 \left(\frac{\text{L}}{\text{year}} \right)$$

Similarly, the reduction in particulate matter (PM) emissions can be estimated by considering both exhausted and non-exhausted emissions, which include emissions from fuel combustion as well as those generated by tire wear, brake wear, and road surface abrasion. Since time saved directly affects the total operational duration of the fleet, the reduction in PM emissions can be calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{PM Reduction (g)} = \left(\text{Exhausted Emissions Factor} \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{hour}} \right) + \text{Non-exhausted Emission Factor} \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{km}} \right) \times \text{Distance (km)} \right) \times \text{Time Saved (hours)}$$

For exhaust emissions, standard emission factors from heavy-duty diesel vehicles can be applied based on regulatory guidelines or empirical fleet data. Non-exhaust emissions will require an estimation of the kilometres travelled and application of recognized coefficients for PM generation per kilometre, typically derived from studies on tire and brake wear. The necessary inputs include the average PM emission rate per hour, the total distance covered by trucks, and the time reduction due to KEYSTONE's implementation. For example, using an factors of 0.5 g/hour and 0.01 g/km per exhausted and non-exhausted emissions correspond, plus a distance travelled of 100 km per day with same time saving and working days than the previous example, it is possible to estimate the PM reduction per year.

$$\text{PM Reduction (g)} = \left(0.5 \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{hour}} \right) + 0.01 \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{km}} \right) \times 100 \text{ (km)} \right) \times 2 \left(\frac{\text{hours}}{\text{day}} \right)$$

$$\text{PM Reduction} \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{day}} \right) = (0.5 + 1) \times 2$$

$$\text{PM Reduction} \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{day}} \right) = 3 \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{day}} \right)$$

$$\text{PM Reduction} \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{day}} \right) = 3 \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{day}} \right) \times 250 \left(\frac{\text{days}}{\text{year}} \right)$$

$$\text{PM Reduction} \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{year}} \right) = 750 \left(\frac{\text{g}}{\text{year}} \right)$$

In addition, the energy savings will be derived from the fuel consumption reduction by incorporating multiplication factors that convert fuel savings into equivalent energy consumption. Diesel fuel has an approximate energy content of 36 MJ/L or 10 kWh/L, which allows for the following estimation:

$$\text{Energy Saved (kWh)} = \text{Fuel Saving (L)} \times \text{Energy Conversion Factor} \left(\frac{\text{kWh}}{\text{L}} \right)$$

By using the previous result, and estimation of 10 kWh/L as energy conversion factor, a simple multiplication is needed:

$$\text{Energy Saved (kWh)} = 17500 \left(\frac{\text{L}}{\text{year}} \right) \times 10 \left(\frac{\text{kWh}}{\text{L}} \right)$$

$$\text{Energy Saved (kWh)} = 175000 \left(\frac{\text{kWh}}{\text{year}} \right)$$

By applying this formula, the total energy saved per year can be determined, reflecting the improved efficiency and reduced environmental footprint achieved through KEYSTONE's digital solutions. The required inputs include the estimated fuel savings from the previous formula and the energy equivalence of diesel.

All three indicators are closely interrelated and directly dependent on time saved during operations. Therefore, a systematic approach to measuring time efficiency at each stage of the logistics chain is fundamental for accurately assessing the sustainability impact of KEYSTONE solutions.

To ensure consistency in evaluation and adaptability to different operational conditions, the estimation of savings will be expressed in percentage reductions rather than fixed absolute values. This approach allows for a relative comparison between the baseline scenario and the post-implementation scenario, ensuring that improvements can be assessed proportionally across various fleet sizes and operational contexts.

Another KPI derive from the time saving is the following (Table 8):

Table 8 Operational KPI - Productivity Based

KPI ID and title	Description
KPI #4: Increase productivity	Increase productivity of the logistics chain on a 10%.

Productivity in transport and logistics operations can be described as the efficiency and effectiveness with which resources (such as fuel, time, and workforce) are utilized to achieve transport objectives, including compliance, cost reduction, and operational optimization. Productivity improvements should reflect the ability to transport goods at lower costs, with fewer delays, and in compliance with regulatory requirements, while maintaining or enhancing service quality. In the case of KEYSTONE, the productivity will be measured by the cost per unit of transport operator at the end of the working day in a year-based scenario.

Other key aspects to evaluate within the operations pertain to the efforts and tasks carried out by the stakeholders involved in the use cases. As outlined in the TO-BE scenarios, enforcement authorities have specific requirements that the KEYSTONE solution aims to address. The following Table 9 presents the KPIs that measure the extent to which these requirements are satisfied by end-users.

Table 9 Operational KPIs – Use Cases

KPI ID and title	Description
KPI #5: Data uploaded through KEYSTONE	70% of total data exchanged is done through KEYSTONE web app.
KPI #6: Time saved during control operations from road enforcement	20% Reduction in the control time from road police enforcer.

These indicators are directly linked to the pain points identified during the gap analysis, which highlighted issues such as the lack of digitization and bottlenecks in information flow. By digitizing processes and streamlining operations, the KEYSTONE solution aims to improve the efficiency and responsiveness of enforcement authorities, enabling them to perform their duties more effectively.

Besides this, KEYSTONE plays a crucial role in facilitating the involvement of external experts, particularly in the context of Task 5.3, "Evaluation with the DTLF working group related to Plug & Play". In this task, Gruber Logistics holds a significant position as an active member of the Digital Transport and Logistics Forum (DTLF) Subgroup 2 – Corridor Information Systems. Their participation ensures that the project remains aligned with the latest developments and best practices within the logistics sector. The KPI for this is listed in Table 10.

Table 10 Operational KPIs - DTLF Group

KPI ID and title	Description
KPI #7: Constant exchange of communication with the DTLF group	Participation in at least five meetings within the DTLF group where KEYSTONE has been discussed.

This KPI is essential for tracking the project's engagement with key stakeholders and ensuring continuous alignment with the evolving Plug & Play framework promoted by the DTLF. Regular participation in these meetings not only strengthens collaboration but also provides valuable insights that can refine and enhance the implementation of KEYSTONE solution across the transport and logistics ecosystem.

3.5.4.2 Technological solution Indicators

To ensure the successful deployment and adoption of KEYSTONE web app, it is crucial to evaluate its performance, usability, and security from the perspective of end-users. Two critical KPIs related to this topic are allocated as Table 11 shows :

Table 11 Technological Solution KPIs – User Acceptance and Accessibility

KPI ID and title	Description
KPI #8: End-user Web app Acceptance	The success of this KPI will be measured by obtaining at least 15/20 in the dedicated stakeholder survey based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM).
KPI #9: Accessibility Tests	Evaluate the accessibility of the web app across various devices (mobile and desktop) and assess the security measures implemented to meet policing software standards.

The evaluation of KEYSTONE web app relies on assessing metrics that measure its effectiveness and usability. One of the critical aspects to consider is end-users' web app usage, which reflects how frequently, and efficiently different stakeholders interact with the platform. This assessment provides valuable insights into whether the web app meets their specific operational needs and expectations. Regular evaluation helps to identify usability issues, uncover areas for improvement, and determine any training requirements needed to enhance user adoption and satisfaction. A thorough understanding of user engagement levels allows the project to refine features, optimize workflows, and improve overall system efficiency. Another essential aspect is accessibility, which ensures that the web app functions effectively across various platforms and devices, including mobile phones, tablets, and desktops. Assessing accessibility involves evaluating whether the web app meets established accessibility standards and security requirements, particularly those relevant to law enforcement software. Compliance with these standards is crucial in enhancing trust among enforcement authorities and logistics stakeholders while also minimizing the risk of unauthorized access or data breaches. By prioritizing accessibility, the project promotes inclusivity and convenience, ensuring that all intended users can fully benefit from the digital ecosystem.

Both KPIs have been defined to measure how effectively the web app meets the needs of its diverse user base, including drivers, enforcement authorities, and logistics managers. These KPIs provide valuable insights into user engagement, accessibility, and compliance with industry standards, ultimately guiding improvements and ensuring alignment with operational and regulatory requirements.

In this context, the web app is only part of KEYSTONE solutions, the web app based its operability on its capacity to collect different data sources and make them available in one single shop, this is allowed by the application of an API (Application Programming Interface) and its reference models ad-hoc.

Table 12 Technological Solution KPIs – API Effectiveness Assessment

KPI ID and title	Description
KPI #10: API Effectiveness and Coverage	90% of anticipated data exchange actions are supported by the APIs derive in the first version.

As previous Table 12 shows, the KPI for assessing the API covers its effectiveness and coverage, by measuring the data exchange actions of the use cases (logistic operators and enforcement authorities) that are effectively supported by APIs derived from the API standard, as defined in the Open API specifications and GitHub Python library (deliverable 2.3, API standard, version 1). The indicator measures the extent to which the API standard supports the specific data exchange required in the pilots, focusing exclusively on logistic to enforcement interactions, it evaluates the pre-pilot completeness and in-pilot adaptability of APIs derived from the standard.

The KPI for the API lies on three stages:

- Pre-piloting Evaluation: definition of the checklist of anticipated data exchange actions for pilot use cases and verification of whether the API Standard covers all actions in the checklist
- During the pilots monitoring: track any unforeseen actions that are not covered by the already defined APIs and the API standard (v1) and find coverage gaps.
- Near the end of pilots - post-pilots’ evaluation: the API standard (v2) will incorporate new actions for identified gaps. We can measure the proportion of the total number of actions.

The following formula will be used for the calculation:

$$Effectiveness\ and\ coverage\ (\%) = \left(\frac{Number\ of\ actions\ effectively\ supported\ by\ API\ standard}{Total\ number\ of\ actions\ required\ during\ the\ pilots} \right) \times 100$$

3.5.4.3 Engagement Indicators

Besides the operational KPIs, KEYSTONE has set indicators to engage the community around the logistics ecosystem, in terms of academia the project has set metrics for incorporating research institutions and open-access publications as Table 13 indicates.

Table 13 Engagement KPIs – Research and Scientific Publications

KPI ID and title	Description
KPI #11: Collaboration with research Institutions	Collaborate and involve at least 10 institutions in Europe within KEYSTONE activities.
KPI #12: Open-access publications	Publish at least 7 open access articles along the project span.

This engagement is not limited to the research institutions but private companies within the ecosystem, in this regard, three indicators for disseminating KEYSTONE’s activities have been defined in the following Table 14.

Table 14 Engagement KPIs – Dissemination

KPI ID and title	Description
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KPI #13: Dissemination activities within EU	Launch at least 1 program of dissemination activities at European level
KPI #14: Workshops between the private sector	Delivery of at least 1 workshop to facilitate collaborations between private companies.
KPI #15: Seminars for the private sector	Organise at least 3 seminars for the private sector (60/90 minutes each, with at least 3 presenters) to facilitate engagement and collaboration.
KPI #16: KEYSTONE community	Creation of a KEYSTONE community including at least 20 European institutions active on the platform.

3.6 Data Collection and Management

Effective data collection and management are crucial to ensuring that the evaluation of KEYSTONE aligns with the established methodologies and accurately measures the project's impact. This chapter outlines the approach to gathering and managing data throughout the pilot phase, focusing on operational and technological indicators that assess the performance, efficiency, and sustainability of KEYSTONE's solutions.

Data collection will follow a structured approach, considering both quantitative and qualitative methods to capture comprehensive insights. The EMs will oversee the data gathering process, ensuring alignment with the defined KPIs and facilitating continuous feedback from stakeholders and end-users. Time reduction estimation will be assessed through automated system logs, and enforcement to measure the efficiency gains introduced by KEYSTONE's solutions. The collection process will involve detailed observations of logistics and enforcement activities, tracking timestamps generated by the web app, and gathering qualitative insights from stakeholders to validate estimated time savings.

The following Table 15 provides a guide of the needed data to be gathered for the KPI's evaluation to be conducted in the consecutive tasks.

Table 15 KPI Data Collection and Management

KPI ID and Title	Data Required from Pilot Sites	Data Collection Method	Source of Data
KPI #1: Energy Saved	Time saved in logistics operations on a year based.	EMs consultation	Logistic operators
KPI #2: PM reduction	Time saved in logistics operations and kilometres travelled, both on a year based.	EMs consultation	Logistic operators
KPI #3: Fuel consumption reduction	Time saved in logistics operations on a year based.	EMs consultation	Logistic operators
KPI #4: Increase productivity	Operation days on a year based.	EMs consultation	Logistic Operators
KPI #5: Data uploaded through KEYSTONE	Number of new data uploaded through KEYSTONE web app.	EMs consultation with the end-users	Logistic Operators – End/Users
KPI #6: Time saved during control operations from road enforcement	A 20% reduction on the control time from road police enforcer.	EMs Consultation to the end user	End-Users

KPI #7: Constant exchange of communication with the DTLF group	Participation in at least five meetings within the DTLF group where KEYSTONE has been discussed.	Task 5.3	Task 5.3
KPI #8: End-user Web Acceptance	The success of this KPI will be measured by obtaining at least 15/20 in the dedicated stakeholder survey based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM).	Survey application (chapter 4.2)	End-users
KPI #9: Accessibility Tests	Evaluate the accessibility of the web app across various devices (mobile and desktop) and assess the security measures implemented to meet policing software standards.	Completion of the WCAG (Web Content Accessibility Guidelines)	CEFRIEL
KPI #10: API Effectiveness and Coverage	Assess the number of data exchange actions covered in the first iteration (v1) of the API standard.	Metric package on back-end	AETHON/T-BRIDGE
KPI #11: Collaboration with research Institutions	Collaborate and involve at least 10 institutions in Europe within KEYSTONE activities.	Partner's report	Project Partners
KPI #12: Open access publications	Publish at least 7 open access articles along the project spam.	Publication tracking	WP6
KPI #13: Dissemination activities within EU	Launch at least 1 program of dissemination activities at European level.	Communication partners	WP6
KPI #14: Workshops between private sector	Delivery of at least 1 workshop to facilitate collaborations between private companies.	Events registers	WP6
KPI #15: Seminars for private sector	Organise at least 3 seminars for the private sector (60/90 minutes each, with at least 3 presenters) to facilitate engagement and collaboration.	Events registers	WP6
KPI #16: KEYSTONE community	Creation of a KEYSTONE community including at least 20 European institutions active on the platform.	Community Analytics Platform	WP6

4. Execution Phase

The execution phase marks a critical stage in the implementation of KEYSTONE, focusing on the operational deployment of the proposed solutions within the identified use cases. This phase is designed to validate the effectiveness, efficiency, and impact of KEYSTONE's solutions in real-world use case scenarios.

The use cases will last a period of three months, during which data will be systematically collected by the EMs who throughout this period will oversee the continuous monitoring of KPIs, ensuring that the data collection aligns with the evaluation methodologies previously defined. These methodologies provide a structured approach to assessing the technological, operational, and socio-economic dimensions of the solution.

A key aspect of the execution phase is the active involvement of stakeholders and end-users at every stage. Their engagement is essential for capturing valuable insights, identifying potential upscale, and ensuring that KEYSTONE's solutions meet their operational needs. To facilitate this, the mechanisms previously described will be established to encourage regular feedback exchanges, fostering an iterative process of assessment and improvement. Feedback will be gathered regularly through contact with the end users, enabling a comprehensive understanding of the user experience and holistic system performance.

Data collected during the execution phase will be systematically transmitted for further evaluation, ensuring alignment with the methodologies outlined in previous chapters. The collected information will serve as the foundation for analyzing the impact of KEYSTONE's solutions in terms of operational efficiency, compliance with regulatory requirements, and overall user satisfaction.

Moreover, a specific focus will be placed on addressing any operational bottlenecks or challenges identified during the execution phase. A responsive approach will be adopted to ensure that corrective actions can be swiftly implemented where necessary, thus maximizing the effectiveness of the solution.

4.1 Deployment Solutions and Initiate Data

The deployment phase begins with the rollout of KEYSTONE solutions within the pilot sites, ensuring that all technical and operational elements are in place. This includes configuring the API Reference Model for seamless data exchange between logistics operators and enforcement authorities and deploying the web app for document verification and compliance monitoring.

Once deployed, the solutions will be monitored in real-time, with the EMs collecting key performance data to track system functionality, user interactions, and process efficiencies. The data collection process will be structured to include:

- baseline assessments to compare pre- and post-implementation scenarios.
- regular performance checks to measure time savings, compliance improvements, and operational efficiencies.
- feedback loops with end-users to identify usability issues and refine functionalities of the solution offered through the implementation of in-situ survey.

This structured approach will ensure that KEYSTONE's digital solutions are effectively validated and optimized before broader implementation, maximizing their impact on the European transport and logistics ecosystem.

4.2 End-users survey

The stakeholder survey plays a crucial role in evaluating user perceptions and acceptance of KEYSTONE solutions, specifically, the web app developed within the project. The survey was designed based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989), a widely recognized framework for assessing digital product adoption. By applying the TAM, the survey aims to assess usability, perceived usefulness, and potential adoption of the web app by the end-users. In a previous step, the survey was already applied for the evaluation of the design of the web app (Metta, Re Calegari, & Agrawal, 2025).

To ensure a user-friendly experience and encourage participation, the survey consists of four concise questions using a 5-point Likert scale. This scale, ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree," allows end-users to express their opinions on key aspects of the web app's functionality and relevance while keeping a simple and effective structure for data collection. The planned approach ensures that the collected data provides measurable insights into user acceptance and identifies potential areas for improvement.

The questions included in the survey focus on the following dimensions:

- perceived value: evaluates whether users find the web app beneficial in their daily operations.
 - "I find this web app valuable."
- ease of use assesses the intuitiveness and clarity of the interface.
 - "The interface is intuitive and easy to understand."
- future adoption: measures the likelihood of continued use beyond the pilot phase.
 - "I see myself using this web app in the near future."
- overall utility: captures an overall rating of the application.
 - "How would you rate this web app?"

The survey is conducted among key end-users engaged in the piloting activities, ensuring that feedback is gathered from those directly interacting with the KEYSTONE solution. The responses will be analysed to determine user satisfaction levels, potential usability challenges, and key areas for optimization, feeding directly into the overall evaluation of the project's impact. By systematically incorporating stakeholder perspectives, the survey serves as an essential tool for validating the effectiveness of KEYSTONE's digital ecosystem and guiding further refinements before full-scale implementation. Additionally, the survey and its results will serve as a KPI for assessing the success of the KEYSTONE application. A predefined success threshold, set at 15/20, will indicate whether the solution effectively meets stakeholder expectations. Achieving this benchmark will validate the web app's usability and its potential for wider adoption within the logistics and enforcement ecosystem.

Besides, the previous questions, the instance will be used to apply the initial part of the AHP, gathering information directly from the end users about the outlined benefits of the KEYSTONE solution.

By systematically incorporating stakeholder perspectives, the survey serves as an essential tool for validating the effectiveness of KEYSTONE's digital ecosystem and guiding further refinements before full-scale implementation.

5. Evaluation Phase

The evaluation phase of KEYSTONE plays a crucial role in assessing the overall impact of the proposed solutions. This phase involves several key tasks, including Task 5.2, Task 5.3, and Task 5.4, each of which is designed to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the project's outcomes. The evaluation will not only focus on measuring the defined KPIs, but it will also incorporate advanced methodologies to ensure a thorough assessment.

Task 5.2 “Evaluation of the impacts of the solutions proposed” involves a detailed analysis of operational and technological aspects to determine the effectiveness of the KEYSTONE solutions in achieving the desired objectives. The task will employ various evaluation methods, such as the AHP, to facilitate decision-making by structuring complex problems into a hierarchy of simpler sub-problems and the CEA to determine the economic feasibility and efficiency of the proposed solutions in terms of resource utilization and operational benefits. Task 5.3 “Evaluation with DTLF working group related to Plug&Play” aims to align the evaluation outcomes with the latest industry standards and stakeholder expectations, ensuring that the KEYSTONE solutions are compatible with existing and emerging digital logistics frameworks, and Task 5.4 “Guidelines for operators, authorities, stakeholders” will translate the evaluation results into actionable insights for stakeholders, policy makers, and industry participants. The guide will serve as a roadmap for future implementation and scalability of KEYSTONE’s solutions, offering practical recommendations based on empirical evidence gathered during the evaluation phase.

Throughout the evaluation phase, the data that has been collected over the three months from the pilot sites will be analyzed using the established methodologies, with continuous involvement of stakeholders and end-users to facilitate an ongoing exchange of feedback. This participatory approach ensures that the evaluation remains dynamic and responsive to the evolving needs of the logistics ecosystem.

5.1 Cost-Effectiveness Analysis

The CEA aims to evaluate the cost/effectiveness ratio of services proposed within KEYSTONE, comparing costs and outcomes. It considers two perspectives: cost per unit of effectiveness and effectiveness per unit of cost. A qualitative questionnaire will first be sent to evaluation managers to assess service efficiency across various areas (environment, finance, society, etc.). Data from this, along with baseline and post-digitalization data, will be mapped on effectiveness scales based on literature and best practices. After implementation, a quantitative survey will gather cost data for a full CEA, combining this with effectiveness results.

With reference to KEYSTONE, the CEA method would measure the following aspects:

1. Cost per Unit of Effectiveness which assesses the financial investment required to achieve specific outcomes for each of the key objectives of the project, that is:
 - Reduced logistics costs: The analysis quantifies the cost savings resulting from more efficient operations, streamlined data sharing, and improved interoperability between transport enforcement authorities and logistics operators.
 - Environmental impact reduction: The CEA calculates the cost-effectiveness of reducing environmental impact through data sharing, consolidation of transport flows, and optimized routes.
 - Improved safety: Evaluate the cost needed to enhance safety through seamless information exchange with enforcement authorities, which could lead to fewer incidents or accidents.
2. Effectiveness per Unit of Cost, which focuses on the benefits achieved relative to the investment made in each area. It would measure:

- **Operational Efficiency:** The extent to which the digital solution and federated approach improve logistics operations for both goods and passengers, reflected in improved efficiency or reduced operational times.
 - **Interoperability Benefits:** How effectively the APIs foster interoperability between different systems, reducing delays or errors in transport operations.
 - **Environmental and Safety Gains:** The degree to which the project reduces environmental harm (e.g., CO2 emissions) and enhances safety by providing real-time data to enforcement authorities.
3. **Comparative Evaluation of Use Cases:** The CEA would compare the performance and cost-effectiveness between the two use cases to assess the scalability and practical impact of the solution in real-world scenarios.

In a nutshell, the CEA will measure the relationship between the investment made in developing and implementing the digital solution and the outcomes achieved in terms of cost savings, environmental benefits, safety improvements, and the acceptance of new technologies.

5.2 Analytical Hierarchical Process

The AHP proposed by Saaty (Saaty, 1990) is a structured decision-making method that helps in systematically evaluating and prioritizing different aspects of a complex problem, especially when multiple criteria need to be considered.

Applied to the development of the KEYSTONE solution, and more specifically to the information collected conducting the activities of Task 4.2 “Definition of the demonstration scenarios”, Task 4.3 “Road transport digital eco-system” and Task 4.4 “Intermodal digital eco-system”. The AHP represents a reproducible and verifiable approach for quantifying the weights of decision criteria, where individual stakeholders’ necessities are utilized to estimate the relative magnitudes of the benefits deriving from the implementation of KEYSTONE solutions through pair-wise comparisons.

The AHP method allows us to reach such a purpose through the following key steps:

1. **Define the Problem and Decision Goal:** Clearly define the key objective, and the goal of the evaluation.
2. **Establish Criteria and Sub-Criteria:** Identify the key criteria that will influence the decision. For more complex problems, sub-criteria can also be established under each main criterion to allow for a finer level of detail.
3. **Structure the Hierarchy:** Organize these elements into a hierarchical structure placing at the top the decision goal, followed by criteria (and potentially sub-criteria), and finally, at the bottom, the various alternatives being considered, if applicable.
4. **Pairwise Comparison of Criteria and Alternatives:** The heart of the AHP method lies in comparing elements (criteria and alternatives) pairwise to determine their relative importance. This is usually done using a scale (e.g., from 1 to 9), where values represent the degree to which one element is more important than another.
5. **Calculate Weights and Scores:** After the pairwise comparisons are made, the relative weights of the criteria are calculated using mathematical methods like eigenvalue analysis. The same is eventually done for the alternatives under each criterion. These weights indicate the importance of each criterion and alternative in the overall decision-making process.
6. **Synthesize Results:** Synthesize the information by aggregating the scores of the alternatives across all criteria. This provides a global ranking of alternatives based on their weighted scores, allowing for a prioritized list of options that best align with the defined goal.

There are several benefits of using the AHP tool, for example, it ensures that all relevant criteria are considered and compared systematically, reducing the chance of overlooking important factors, also, it is a highly transparent process, with every comparison and the rationale behind it clearly documented. Besides,

it allows us to make subjective judgments, mathematically processed to minimize bias. Furthermore, both quantitative and qualitative criteria can be evaluated together in a balanced manner.

Being, therefore, a very reliable analytical method to systematically investigate and prioritize different aspects of a complex system by breaking down decision-making factors into a hierarchical structure where each criterion is assessed based on its relative importance and impact, it's been applied in different EU projects, for example in FENIX, a logistic project that implemented a federated connector similar to KEYSTONE solution but mostly for private actors, which under its common evaluation framework (Renzi, et al., 2022) applies a methodology consisting of a six-step approach that is followed for each pilots site's use cases and services, specifically the step 5 which focuses on assessing the impact of the use of digitalization by using the tools and methods developed in previous steps. The task performs a Multi Criteria Analysis (MCA) to provide a single impact assessment value per eco-system and an AHP in case of different options. More in detail, the Experience & impact assessment (EIA) uses the KPIs which were developed for each eco-system, and which were quantified with respect to their baselines and after digitalization. Then, different weights for each KPI are developed and applied for each eco-system using MCA and AHP. The result of this approach is an indicator for the EIA which provides an easy-to-understand measure of the impact of digitalization.

Another EU project that applied the AHP was 5G-LOGINNOV (Renzi, 2022), that by given the challenges of collecting reliable data for AHP, particularly in complex contexts with hard-to-reach stakeholders, it has developed a new AHP methodology built on Saaty's approach. This European project focuses on optimizing port operations through 5G technologies, IoT, AI/ML, data analytics, next-generation traffic management, and CCAM. The importance of various 5G applications and services was assessed based on stakeholder perceptions and insights from port technology and operations workers. The research question driving this work was: "Which 5G service best addresses the most urgent needs of ports?". Data was first adjusted according to the project's specific needs and then analysed using the AHP method. The results showed that even if the AHP can help in providing an overall ranking of specific alternatives, the ranking can be very sensitive, with even small changes in priority weights potentially altering the final order of alternatives. Still, AHP enables periodic checks throughout the project to ensure the objectives and criteria remain relevant, helping to clarify the strengths of use cases and prioritize services for better dissemination and exploitation of results.

With reference to KEYSTONE, the AHP method will allow us to indicate the most important benefit achieved with the introduction of the KEYSTONE solution, according to the stakeholders. Based on what has been accomplished so far during the piloting phase and the relevant data collected to date from the three categories of stakeholders already identified: truck drivers, port authorities, and enforcement authorities.

Regarding the criteria for conducting the entire survey, the needs that may be most relevant among the three categories of stakeholders and that could be met through the implementation of the KEYSTONE solution have been identified, specifically:

1. Propagation in more European regions and among various stakeholders.
2. Reducing time in logistical processes (for example, loading/unloading, and document management).
3. Increased productivity and resource utilization.
4. Reduction of operational costs through automation and digitalization.
5. Adaptability to different regulatory contexts.
6. Reduction of fuel consumption and emissions.

These criteria will be integrated into the survey (chapter 4.2), with the format and platform to be subsequently defined, which will be submitted by the EMs to all stakeholders to gather the necessary data for the pair-wise comparison matrix.

Of course, the list of criteria above has been formulated preliminarily and may change in the coming months, depending on the outputs of the piloting activities and the project evaluation.

5.3 Guide for consolidation of findings and recommendations

The consolidation of the pilot results conducted in the KEYSTONE project represents an essential step for the formulation of evidence-based recommendations aimed at supporting decision makers in the definition of strategies and actions for the adoption of a fully digital transport ecosystem. The formulation of such evidence-based recommendations relies on the evidence generated during the experimental program and the associated impact evaluations carried out within WP5.

This process will entail three phases:

- Review of pilot findings and lessons learnt
 - Review of the evidence from the pilots, with a focus on lessons learnt
 - Identification of key success drivers, barriers, and restraining factors that emerged during the experiments.
 - Reviewing KPIs and further analyses conducted in WP5, including the assessment of economic sustainability through CEA.
- Formulation of evidence-based recommendations
 - Structuring the recommendations in a multi-level framework addressing both the needs of industry players and the priorities of public authorities.
 - Development of operational guidance for policy makers at the National and European levels on the regulatory and technological aspects required for the transition to a fully digital transport ecosystem
- Definition of a set of concrete actions to facilitate the adoption of the solutions tested in the pilots.
 - Dissemination and presentation of the recommendations
 - Drafting of a white paper incorporating the recommendations developed
 - Presentation of the paper at major international events (e.g. ITS World Congress, IRF Congress, TRA) to involve key stakeholders and promote debate on the future of digitalisation in transport.
 - Dissemination of the white paper through institutional platforms and sector associations at the National and International level, including the TTS' Local Authorities Platform and the International Road Federation.

5.4 Methodological Considerations

In evaluating the KEYSTONE solutions, several methodological considerations must be acknowledged to ensure the robustness and validity of the results. These considerations pertain to the limitations and challenges associated with data reliability and variability, the applicability of indicators across both use cases, and internal factors that may influence the outcomes.

A key methodological challenge lies in data reliability and variability. Given the dynamic nature of logistics operations and the diversity of stakeholders involved, inconsistencies in data collection may arise. Factors such as differences in data recording practices, variations in operational schedules, and discrepancies in stakeholder engagement levels can introduce variability. To mitigate this, standardized data collection methods and consistent communication with EMs will be implemented. Additionally, efforts will be made to validate the data through cross-checking with multiple sources, thereby enhancing the reliability of the findings.

The applicability of indicators across both use cases is another important consideration. KEYSTONE involves two distinct use cases: monomodal and intermodal logistics operations. Although these scenarios share certain operational similarities, they also exhibit unique characteristics that may influence the measurement of KPIs. For example, time saved in logistics operations may have different implications in a monomodal versus an intermodal context, due to variations in operational complexity and modal transfers. Therefore, it

is crucial to interpret the indicators in the context of each use case while ensuring comparability. This will involve adapting the KPIs to account for the specific operational dynamics of each scenario, thus preserving the validity of cross-use-case comparisons.

Internal factors impacting the results must also be considered. These factors include the level of stakeholder engagement, the technological readiness of the users, and the overall adaptability of the logistics operations to KEYSTONE solutions. Variations in stakeholder participation can significantly impact the data collected, particularly for indicators related to user satisfaction and operational efficiency. Moreover, differences in technological infrastructure and digital literacy levels among stakeholders can influence the effectiveness of the solutions, potentially skewing the evaluation results. To address this, the evaluation will account for these internal factors by documenting contextual conditions and considering them in the interpretation of results. This approach ensures that the findings are reflective of real-world operational environments.

Another methodological limitation relates to the generalization of findings. The piloting phase involves two specific use cases within defined geographical and operational contexts, which may limit the generalizability of the results to other logistics scenarios. Although the use cases were carefully selected to represent typical logistics operations, the unique characteristics of each site may affect the scalability and replicability of the solutions. To address this, the evaluation will include a contextual analysis to identify the specific conditions under which the solutions were tested. This analysis will provide insights into the scalability of the findings and inform the development of guidelines for broader implementation.

Finally, the use of multiple evaluation methodologies, including the AHP, CEA, and Scenario-Based Testing, introduces complexity in the interpretation of results. While this multi-method approach enhances the comprehensiveness of the evaluation, it also poses challenges in terms of data integration and interpretation. To overcome this, a consistent analytical framework will be applied, ensuring the alignment of findings across methodologies and enabling a holistic understanding of the solutions' impact.

By acknowledging these methodological considerations and adopting appropriate mitigation strategies, the evaluation of KEYSTONE solutions will be more robust and reflective of real-world operational dynamics.

6. Implementation Time-Plan

The following subchapter explains the timeline and the milestones to accomplish the data collection and evaluation within the pilot sites.

6.1 Timeline

The implementation plan is designed to measure the effectiveness and impact of the proposed digital ecosystem through the set of defined KPIs, specifically regarding to the operativity. Those indicators will be assessed during the piloting phase, which starts on M25 and continues until M30, under task 4.3 “Road transport digital eco-system” and task 4.4 “Intermodal digital eco-system”, lead by Gruber and CIM respectively. These activities will test in real-world the monomodal and intermodal case, validating the solution’s performance in their operational environments, with their stakeholder acting, offering a comprehensive insight into the impact. Lately, the result from the activities will be systematically reported to the task 5.2 “Evaluation of the impacts of the solutions proposed”, which is mainly responsible for the evaluation of the impact of KEYSTONE’s solutions. This process measures the operational efficiency, environmental benefits, and stakeholder acceptance of the digital ecosystem.

During the Execution phase, data collected from the piloting activities will be continually communicated to task 5.2 through the EMs, ensuring alignment between the pilot activities and the evaluation objectives. This iteration feedback loop will facilitate ongoing adjustments and refinements in the deployment of the solutions, ensuring accuracy and relevance in the holistic impact assessment.

6.2 Milestones

To ensure timely data collection, effective communication with the EMs and comprehensive impact assessment and facilitate the tracking and monitoring of the progress and act quickly before any possible risk, the following milestones are being set strategically:

- **Milestone 1 - Establishment of the baseline (M25):** the baseline for the operational KPIs will be established at the early stage of the piloting, this activity involves estimation of the current state of operations pre-implementation of the KEYSTONE solutions, providing the benchmarking against the improvement can be measured. This process includes metrics such as:
 - Time spent in the logistic chain relative to the project
 - Distance travelled during the logistic chain relative to the project
- **Milestone 2 – First Data Collection and Survey Application (M27):** by the first two months of the piloting is expected to have the first data collection, by capturing initial performance metrics from the deployment of the KEYSTONE solution. This milestone also marks the implementation of the survey application to gather feedback from end-users, including drivers, enforcement authorities, and port authorities. Among the data to be collected are intends to gather metrics for the operation but also technological solutions KPIs.
- **Milestone 3 – Final Data Collection and Preliminary Analysis (M30):** At the end of the piloting period, a comprehensive data collection will be completed. This will be used as a second iteration for comparing the data against the baselines to evaluate the impact of KEYSTONE solutions.

This structured timeline and milestone approach ensures that the piloting activities are aligned with the evaluation objectives defined. By coordinating data collection and reporting processes, the evaluation team can accurately assess the impact of KEYSTONE solutions across operational, environmental, and stakeholder engagement dimensions.

The results from the piloting phase will be instrumental in validating the effectiveness of the solutions, identifying areas for improvement, and providing data-driven recommendations for future development and deployment.

7. Conclusions

The document provides a comprehensive overview of the methodology, metrics, and evaluation framework employed to assess the impact of KEYSTONE's digital solutions on real-world logistics operations.

Key to this study is the structured approach to evaluation, which incorporates the V scheme of FOT analysis, adapted specifically for KEYSTONE. Besides, this document laid out clear objectives, roles, and KPIs, setting the foundation for the subsequent assessment activities foreseen at the end of task 5.2 "*Evaluation of the impacts of the solutions proposed*" (M25 – M32).

Indeed, the advanced analytical methodologies outlined in the present document, such as the AHP, and CEA, as well as the specific KPIs identified, serve as a critical guide for the upcoming evaluation phases, particularly after the completion of the piloting phase (WP4). As such, it will be crucial for the preparation of D5.2, which will comprehensively assess the impact of the proposed solutions in both intermodal and monomodal transport use cases, following the metrics herewith described.

In conclusion, the present document provides the framework for future data-based evaluation work and ensures that the project remains aligned with its general goals, ultimately driving the development of an effective and sustainable digital logistics solution at the EU level.

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